

Monitoring Gravity for the NIST-4 Watt Balance

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Abstract — The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) new watt balance (NIST-4) has been constructed for the realization of mass through an exact value of the Planck constant in the new International System of Units (SI). The total relative uncertainty goal for the instrument of a few parts in 10^8 requires the determination of the local acceleration of gravity, g , with parts in 10^9 accuracy at the location of the mass at the time mechanical and electrical forces are being compared. We describe the procedures used and give results for the measurements of the local acceleration of gravity in the new watt balance facility.

Index Terms — fundamental constants, Planck constant, gravity, international system of units, watt balance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Resolution 1 of the 24th Meeting of the General Conference on Weights and Measures (CGPM) outlines a revised SI based upon fixed numerical values of invariants of nature [1]. A consequence is that the unit of mass will be realized through an assigned value of the Planck constant, h . One method of realizing mass in the revised SI uses an instrument called a watt balance [2] where in one mode the gravitational force on a mass is compared to an electrical force. To summarize the operational principle of a watt balance, the measurements involved relate the Planck constant to mass, length, and time through

$$m = hC/gv \quad (1)$$

where m is the mass of an artifact mass standard, g is the local acceleration of gravity, v is a velocity, and C is a combination of frequencies and scalar constants. To realize mass in the revised SI, NIST has constructed a new watt balance, NIST-4 [3], that is presently taking preliminary data to be used in the pilot study for the mass *mise en pratique* [4].

To realize mass with a total uncertainty at a few parts in 10^8 , equation (1) highlights the importance of determining g at the location of the mass at the time of the force comparison to an accuracy of a few parts in 10^9 such that the uncertainty in g does not significantly contribute to the final watt balance result. The challenge in determining g at the precise mass location and time of force comparison is that the instrument is physically in the way. An initial investigation of measuring, mapping, and/or modeling the gravity gradients in the NIST-4

laboratory to establish a tie between the mass position and a stable gravity observation station nearby was recently completed [5]. We present a confirmation of the investigation together with real time monitoring of g during NIST-4 operation.

To stay consistent with the field of absolute gravimetry, the non SI unit of acceleration, the gal (symbol Gal) is used in this text. It is defined as $1 \text{ Gal} = 1 \text{ cm/s}^2$ [6].

II. THE NIST-4 LABORATORY

The laboratory for the NIST-4 watt balance is a two-story tall subterranean room on the sub-basement level of an underground structure, building 218, room E024 (218/E024). The depth is approximately 12 m below the surface, located close to the building limits to the south and west. The building extends below the natural water table and therefore has a subsurface pumping and drainage system, collecting ground water in a sump at the north-east part of the building before removed to a nearby surface collection area. The top of the building is covered with a thick layer of soil. A storm drain along the north and south sides of the building collects excess surface water. The watt balance itself sits on the center of an isolated 60 ton concrete slab, 4 m x 4 m x 2.4 m high. The subterranean location of 218/E024 and the mass distribution of the concrete structure of the lab creates significant non-uniform gravity gradients.

III. DETERMINING ABSOLUTE GRAVITY AT THE MASS POSITION

Absolute g determinations were made in July 2013 and September 2015 in the southwest (SW) corner of the slab using a Micro- g LaCoste freefall gravimeter [7], model FG5-204*, giving consistent results within $\pm 1.5 \mu\text{Gal}$. In order to determine absolute gravity at the mass location, a series of vertical translations and a tie to the symmetry axis of the magnet were made using a Scintrex CG5 Autograv relative gravimeter* [8] (see Figure 1). For the 2015 determination, the heights of the ties were chosen to reduce the amount of vertical translation needed. Also for the 2015 determination, the vertical gravity gradient on the symmetry axis of the magnet was carefully re-measured due to the highly nonlinear gradient from the 800 kg mass of the magnet (see Figure 2).

Fig. 1: Diagram showing the procedure to determine absolute g at the mass position on the watt balance with the absolute measurements made at the SW location.

Fig. 2: Vertical gravity gradient of NIST-4 above the magnet along the vertical concentric symmetry axis, where the test mass will be located.

IV. SUMMARY

First measurements of the local acceleration of gravity, vertical gravity gradients, and mapping of gravity as a function of horizontal position of the NIST laboratory 218/E024 have been made. A value for g of $980103142.5(4.4) \mu\text{Gal}$ has been determined in September 2015. A total uncertainty of only 4.5×10^{-9} was obtained, well within the necessary range required by the watt balance experiment and in good agreement with the previously reported value of $980103140.2(4.3) \mu\text{Gal}$ from measurements taken in July 2013 [5]. Long-term absolute gravity observations at the SW corner of the slab have been started and first data shows a seasonal change of g in the order of a few μGals within a few weeks (see Figure 3).

However, no signs of changes of gradients in the room have been observed so far, but more frequent gradient and tie measurements need to be completed in the near future to determine the frequency of which those measurements need to be performed to allow a continuous watt balance operation within the uncertainty goal.

A superconducting gravimeter at a nearby location has recently been monitoring relative seasonal gravity deviations. These results, along with environmental monitoring of water table, rainfall, and global pressure variations will be presented.

Fig. 3: Absolute gravity observations over 3 months in the NIST-4 laboratory in the SW corner. The stated uncertainties are combined set standard deviations only.

*Any commercial equipment, instruments, or materials identified in this paper are to foster understanding. Such identification does not imply recommendation or endorsement, nor does it imply that the material or equipment are necessarily the best available

REFERENCES

- [1] <http://www.bipm.org/en/worldwide-metrology/cgpm/resolutions.html>.
- [2] B.P. Kibble, "A measurement of the gyromagnetic ratio of the proton by the strong field method," in *Atomic Masses and Fundamental Constants 5*, edited by J.H. Sanders and A.H. Wapstra, pp. 545–551 (1976).
- [3] D. Haddad, L. S. Chao, F. Seifert, D. B. Newell, J. R. Pratt, S. Schlamminger, "First mass measurements with the NIST-4 watt balance," this conference
- [4] <http://www.bipm.org/en/committees/cc/cem/publications-cc.html>
- [5] E. J. Leaman, D. Haddad, F. Seifert, L. S. Chao, A. Cao, J. R. Pratt, S. Schlamminger, and D. B. Newell, "A Determination of the Local Acceleration of Gravity for the NIST-4 Watt Balance," *IEEE Trans Inst. and Meas.*, **64**(6), 1663-1669, (2015)
- [6] The International System of Units (SI), 8th edition, 2006; updated in 2014 (Sèvres, France: Bureau International des Poids et Mesures), table 9, <http://www.bipm.org/en/publications/si-brochure/table9.html>.
- [7] Micro-g LaCoste, 1401 Horizon Ave., Lafayette, CO 80026
- [8] Scintrex Limited, 222 Snidercroft Road, Concord, L4K 2K1 Ontario, Canada